

STRENGTHENING THE HOSPITAL HEALTHCARE BY CLUSTERING RESOURCES ON REGIONS: A NEW PERSPECTIVE

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Introduction

A strengthening the national healthcare system requires efficient allocation of resources to provide equitable access to hospital healthcare with its acceptable quality for all. For the specific patient, the role of time spent for diagnosing and treating as well as their effectiveness and safety becomes crucial this time.

Study objective

To evaluate economically and structurally the possibility of development country- and region (viloyat) level medical clusters as a way to increase efficiency of resources allocated for hospital care.

Materials and methods

A review of national regulations regarding management of hospital healthcare with retrospective analysis of the cost in hospital care centers in Tashkent city and regions' capitals followed by the evaluation and prognosis of risk of the costs in the newly suggested multispecialty hospitals.

Results

This time, the highly specialized inpatient care is being provided by 155 small size (60-150 beds and 35-150 visits/day) hospitals with consulting units and their branches in Tashkent city and the regions' capitals. On every such hospital is employed more than 80 staff assistants and administrative personnel units, totally contributing to additional 13,000 staff number. The annual cost for salary and social insurance payments, for this staff, became equal to 1.8 tn. sums (140 mil. USD). In case this amount saved, one can build a large additional medical cluster for one year, in the regions. In addition to the decrease the need on the local administrative staff, development of the up-to-date medical clusters, in the regions, can contribute contract-based relations on purchasing the healthcare, totally following annual up to 100 bn. sums saved. The specialized centers (hospitals) are located on eleven state owned objects, in every region. To store all buildings and equipment in these objects, the government spends 0.45-1.2 tn. sums and to maintain them – up to 0.31-0.77 tn. sums annually. For a development of multispecialty medical cluster for 800-1000 beds and 1000 visits/day, there needs to be invested about 120-130 mil. USD on every region. Some investments costs can be compensated by privatizing unoccupied public buildings and equipment and resources that will be reallocated after closing the small size hospitals.

Discussion

The analysis demonstrated that small size specialty oriented regional hospitals had high weight of administrative costs, low efficiency in the use of highly qualified workforce with

diagnostic and curative equipment. Most important is that an examination of every patient requires 3-5 days, and they need to visit several clinics and specialists.

Conclusions

1. The development of large size multispecialty medical clusters in the country and regional level will provide higher allocative efficiency of resources in comparison with the use of small size clinics and their branches.
2. The investments planned to provide for the development of multispecialty medical clusters can be compensated by saved budget spendings and privatizing newly unoccupied public buildings and equipment.